

Full Length Article

Flexible calcium looping for CO₂ capture in electric Arc Furnace steelmaking: A techno-economic analysisNéstor D. Montiel-Bohórquez ^{ID}*, Manuele Gatti, Matteo C. Romano*

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a techno-economic analysis of four configurations of the Calcium Looping (CaL) technology, tailored to enhance system flexibility for capturing CO₂ from the fluctuating flue gases generated by a scrap-based Electric Arc Furnace with a capacity of 112 t_{steel}/h. The configurations differ based on the solids circulation strategy between reactors (constant or variable) and the presence of one or two intermediate solids storage vessels. Configurations incorporating intermediate solids storage demonstrated operational advantages, including enhanced process stability and downsized calciner island components. Moreover, the plant configuration with two intermediate solids storages led to the lowest specific fuel consumption of 5.85 MJ per kg_{CO2} captured. Under the assumptions considered, the CaL system achieved a CO₂ capture rate of 91 % from the EAF off-gas. Moreover, using residual forestry biomass as fuel in the calciner enabled to achieve negative emissions with net CO₂ removal rates of 13-26 t_{CO2}/h, corresponding to 100-200 kg_{CO2} removed per t_{steel} produced. From an economic standpoint, increment in steel cost ranged from 26 to 36 €/t_{steel} (assuming a carbon tax of 100 €/t_{CO2}), with costs of CO₂ avoided of 202-255 €/t_{CO2}.

1. Introduction

The Iron and Steel (I&S) sector is the largest industrial contributor to global CO₂ emissions, accounting for 29 % of industry-related emissions (IEA, 2022) and approximately 7 % of total energy-related CO₂ emissions worldwide (IEA, 2020). Given steel's crucial role in economic growth and technological development, including renewable energy infrastructure, global steel demand is expected to rise substantially (Kim et al., 2022). Currently, the dominant steel production route is the Blast Furnace-Basic Oxygen Furnace (BF-BOF) process, representing 70 % of global steel output, followed by scrap-based Electric Arc Furnace (EAF, 23 %) and Direct Reduction Iron-EAF (DRI-EAF, 7 %) routes. Nonetheless, due to its lower emission intensity (scope 1 and 2) of 0.3-0.5 t_{CO2}/t_{hot metal} for scrap-EAF and 0.7-1.3 t_{CO2}/t_{hot metal} for DRI-EAF, compared to BF-BOF (2.0-2.2 t_{CO2}/t_{hot metal}) (Perpiñán et al., 2023), the share of EAF-based routes is expected to grow, along with the use of low-carbon fuels, as a decarbonization strategy in the I&S sector. However, these strategies alone will not be sufficient to meet the required CO₂ reduction targets (Sun et al., 2022). Therefore, carbon capture will be essential to significantly abate the process-related CO₂ emissions from steelmaking.

To date, research on implementing carbon capture in I&S has primarily focused on BF-BOF integrated mills, including pre-combustion,

post-combustion, and oxy-combustion approaches (Perpiñán et al., 2023; Leeson et al., 2017; Gazzani et al., 2015; Arasto et al., 2013; Tsu-pari et al., 2013), as this is the most widespread and CO₂-intensive steelmaking route. Integrating carbon capture into EAF steelmaking presents specific challenges due to the highly fluctuating properties of the flue gases to be treated and to the variable and low average CO₂ concentration. Thus, flexible CO₂ capture systems capable of operating efficiently under variable flue gas flow rate, CO₂ content, and temperature should be designed. To date, few studies have assessed CO₂ capture processes from EAF based on oxycombustion and post-combustion technologies, with simplified approaches considering average gas properties (Bonacina et al., 2024; Pires et al., 2025).

Calcium Looping (CaL) has emerged as a promising carbon capture technology in industrial processes. Different works comparing the performance of CaL with other carbon capture technologies have highlighted the advantages of applying CaL in cement production (Vold-sund et al., 2019; Gardarsdottir et al., 2019; Atsonios et al., 2015), BF-BOF steelmaking (Cormos, 2016; Tian et al., 2018), and power production (Vorrías et al., 2013; Haaf et al., 2020). These studies suggest that CaL offers higher potential CO₂ capture rates and the possibility of power production (while requiring additional low-grade fuel and oxygen), which leads to lower energy imports and economic penalties compared with benchmark technologies.

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Nomenclature

Acronyms

ASU	air separation unit
BF-BOF	blast furnace-basic oxygen furnace
CaL	calcium looping
CAPEX	capital expenditures
CCA	cost of CO ₂ avoided
CCR	CO ₂ capture rate
CC	carbon capture
CFB	Circulating fluidised bed
CFD	computational fluid dynamics
CPU	CO ₂ purification unit
CSP	concentrated solar power
DRI	direct reduced iron
EAF	electric arc furnace
FBHE	fluidised bed heat exchanger
LOX	liquid oxygen
MPC	multivariable predictive control
NPV	net present value
OPEX	operational expenditures
O&M	operation and maintenance
SC	steam cycle
TES	thermal energy storage
TPC	total plant cost

Symbols

ΔC_{steel}	increment of steel cost [€/t _{steel}]
\dot{m}	mass flow rate [kg/s]
\dot{n}	mole flow rate [kmol/s]
\dot{P}	electric power [MW]
E_{carb}	carbonator CO ₂ capture efficiency
$E_{\text{EAF, off-gas}}$	CO ₂ capture efficiency referred to the EAF off-gas
F_0	mole flow of fresh makeup limestone [kmol/s]
F_{Ca}	mole flow of CaO-sorbent cycling from the calciner to the carbonator [kmol/s]
F_{CO_2}	mole flow of CO ₂ in flue gas entering the carbonator [kmol/s]
SFC	specific fuel consumption [MJ/kg _{CO2}]
X_{ave}	average carbonation degree of the CaO-sorbent in the solid population
$X_{\text{max,ave}}$	maximum average carbonation degree of the CaO-sorbent in the solid population

Several studies have proposed flexible CaL configurations with intermediate solids storage for thermal energy storage in concentrated solar power plants and CO₂ capture from coal power plants with variable load (Table 1), none of them testing experimentally at relevant scale the integration with the solid storage concept. A CaL configuration featuring intermediate solids storage was initially proposed for concentrated solar power plants where solids (CaCO₃) are calcined using concentrated solar heat and stored in a CaO reservoir at 30 °C. Subsequently, CaO carbonation takes place in a pressurised reactor and the hot gases produced are expanded in a gas turbine to produce power (Edwards and Materić, 2012). More recently, Ortiz et al. (2018) analysed the techno-economic performance of different novel CaL schemes for energy storage in concentrated solar power plants, proposing high-temperature solid storage to simplify heat integration. The application of a CaL system with intermediate solid storage for carbon capture applications was first discussed in the patent by Abanades et al. (2014). Subsequently, several studies have been conducted to assess the techno-economic performance of CaL configurations with intermediate solid storage for carbon capture in coal-fired power plants with variable load (Hanak et al., 2016; Criado et al., 2017; Astolfi et al., 2019). Findings indicate that intermediate sorbent storage enhances plant operation by mitigating the effects of

varying flue gases in the calciner island. Additionally, it improves system economics by allowing for the downsizing of the calciner, ASU, and CPU. Finally, Astolfi et al. (2021) explored the integration of additional solid storage in the calciner line to provide the system with increased flexibility in response to variations in power demand.

Based on the results reported in the cited literature on post-combustion CO₂ capture, the implementation of intermediate solid storage in the CaL systems can potentially address issues related to variable flue gases, although it will also increase system complexity. Moreover, there are still several questions related to the feasibility of CaL configurations with intermediate solid storage, such as experimental demonstration—where the fluidisation of solids in the storage vessels should be addressed—and optimisation of process integration and techno-economic performance. Previous studies have focused on the application of flexible CaL systems to power plants, where daily and weekly cycling were simulated (Astolfi et al., 2019, 2021). In contrast, much more rapid fluctuations are expected in industrial processes, such as the EAF steelmaking system analysed in this work (see Fig. 1), and the feasibility of flexible CaL configurations needs to be addressed for these particular operating conditions.

Ylätaalo et al. (2014) and Cormos and Simon (2015) employed two different 1D dynamic models to investigate the operation of the circulating fluidized bed (CFB) CaL reactors under variable gas flow rates. Their studies demonstrated that CaL reactors can maintain high capture efficiency under different operating conditions derived from the operation of flexible power plants. For instance, Ylätaalo simulated partial load variations from 0 %-100 % and obtained capture efficiencies above 80 % for all the simulated points. To achieve this, precise control of the fluidisation regime (gas recirculation), internal solids circulation, and the make-up input is essential for sustaining high capture efficiencies under partial load. Similar findings were reported from experiments conducted at a 1.7 MW_{th} pilot-scale CaL facility by Diego and Arias (2020). Nonetheless, it should be noted that such precise control strategies and the dynamic operation of CaL systems are still open challenges that should be addressed via numerical and experimental/piloting studies.

Previous studies focused on variable flue gases from power plants, where fluctuations are limited to flow rate and occur on an hourly or daily basis. However, as depicted in Fig. 1, flue gases from the EAF exhibit rapid fluctuations in flow rate, composition, and temperature. Additionally, these variations occur on a much shorter timescale (e.g. minutes) compared to power plants. This means that the operation of the CaL system under such rapidly changing conditions should be investigated. While advanced modelling approaches (e.g., 1D dynamic and transient CFD) are needed to develop novel reactor designs and experimental tests must be carried out to demonstrate the concepts, process analysis should be carried out to assess the impact of novel plant configurations in the performance of the entire CO₂ capturing system.

Accordingly, this work conducts a process design and techno-economic assessment of CaL integration for capturing CO₂ from EAF off-gases. It evaluates the performance of a CaL system utilising circulating fluidised bed (CFB) reactors. Several strategies aimed at enhancing the flexibility of the CaL plant are explored and compared by defining different case scenarios and plant configurations. The analysis accounts for the off-design operation of the plant components under variable load; however, evaluating the CaL reactor dynamic response is beyond the scope of this study. The novel contributions from this work are: i) defining different process designs for implementing and operating a CaL system with fluctuating EAF flue gases; ii) presenting a comprehensive techno-economic analysis of the CaL technology for CO₂ capture from a scrap-EAF. To the best of the author's knowledge, no prior studies addressed this specific application.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 describes the EAF off-gas properties (Section 2.1), the different CaL configuration integrated

Table 1
Literature analysing the integration of intermediate solids storage in CaL systems.

Reference	Type	Application	Main characteristics
Edwards and Materić (2012)	Process modelling	Solar power production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy storage through solar calcination/carbonation. • Pressurized carbonator coupled to a gas turbine. • Solids stored at low temperature (30 °C). • Theoretical plant energy efficiency: 40% - 46%
Abanades et al. (2014)	Patent	Power production, carbon capture (CC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For large-scale energy storage in power plants using CFB combustors. The energy is stored in the form of sensible heat (hot solids). • Suitable for CaL systems for CO₂ capture, where the carbonation reaction improves the energy storage capacity.
Hanak et al. (2016)	Techno-economic analysis	CC in coal-fired power plants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Several energy storage routes: CaO/CaCO₃ solid storage, CaO/Ca(OH)₂/CaCO₃ solids storage, and cryogenic O₂ storage. • CaO/CaCO₃ and CaO/Ca(OH)₂/CaCO₃ routes have a low impact on economic indicators. • All the routes have a positive impact on the economic performance.
Criado et al. (2017)	Process modelling	CC in back-up coal-fired power plants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbonator temperatures (500–600 °C) are compatible with low-temperature solid storage (< 250 °C) • Reduction in electricity cost up to 30% compared to CaL without solid storage.
Ortiz et al. (2018)	Process modelling	Solar power production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High temperature solids storage to simplify heat integration. • Four novel process schemes are explored. • Net electric power-to-calciner heat input ratios of 0.32-0.44
Astolfi et al. (2019)	Process modelling	CC in coal-fired power plants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solids storage at high temperatures. • CaL with and without solid storage, including part-load analysis. • Reduction in the cost of CO₂ avoided between 16–26% compared to the CaL configuration without solids storage.
Astolfi et al. (2021)	Process modelling	CC in coal-fired power plants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secondary storage for solids from the calciner. • External solid heat exchanger to recover the carbonation reaction heat. • Reduction in the capital cost by 4–5%.
Kettunen and Rosnell (2024)	Patent	CC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intermediate solid storage to buffer variations in the composition of solids from the carbonator to the calciner. • Discuss methods to operate the fluidised solid storage.

Fig. 1. Properties of EAF off-gases used as inputs for simulations: a) Actual volumetric flow rate [Am^3/s], b) CO₂ concentration, wet basis [mol/mol], c) CO₂ molar flow rate [kmol/s], and d) Temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]. **Note:** Each subplot includes the histogram with the distribution of the corresponding EAF off-gas property (numbers of bins = 30).

to the EAF (Section 2.2), as well as the methodology followed to simulate the plant and conduct the techno-economic analysis Section 2.3–2.5. Next, results are reported in Section 3 along with their discussion. Finally, conclusions are included in Section 4.

2. Methodology

This section presents the methods used to conduct the techno-economic analysis of the calcium looping plant to capture CO₂ from EAF off-gas.

2.1. EAF off-gas

The flue gases generated in EAF steelmaking plants display significant variability in properties due to the batch-based nature of the process. Each tap-to-tap cycle, which typically spans 50 to 90 minutes, comprises phases of minimal flue gas production (such as during charging and tapping) as well as phases of peak production (such as during melting and refining) (Gandt et al., 2016). The flue gas properties used in the current analysis—flow rate, composition, and temperature—were measured in an EAF steelmaking plant located in Norway (Swerin,

2024). The steel production capacity is 112 t/h, while the CO₂ emissions (Scope 1) are 11.52 t/h. The profiles of EAF off-gas volumetric flow rate, CO₂ concentration (wet basis), and temperature are presented in Fig. 1. The plotted profiles, lasting 930 minutes, were obtained after pre-processing the dataset to remove non-reliable measurements. Significant variability is observed for all three properties; the maximum gas flow rate (224 Am³/s) is two orders higher than the minimum value (4 Am³/s). Similarly, CO₂ concentration peaks at 25 mol.% and drops to 0 mol.%, while the temperature varies in the range from 1190 °C down to 175 °C. Besides, the transition between these minimum and peak values spans approximately 25 minutes without a perfectly cyclic behaviour in two consequent peak-to-peak periods. Consequently, CO₂ capture systems implemented in EAF steelmaking plants must be designed to handle such high variability, ensuring smooth plant operation and that average capture rates align with mitigation targets and meet CO₂ quality specifications.

2.2. CaL Plant applied to EAF steelmaking

This section describes the general structure of the CaL plant integrated into EAF steelmaking. The idea is to give an overall description of the main sections and processes in the CaL plant (Section 2.2.1). Then, the description of a set of strategies implemented to improve the flexibility of the CaL plant to treat the EAF off-gas is presented in Section 2.2.2.

2.2.1. General CaL plant description

Fig. 2 illustrates a schematic representation of the CaL plant applied to Electric Arc Furnace (EAF) steelmaking as an end-of-pipe carbon capture technology. The CaL plant consists of five main subsystems: i) the EAF off-gas cooling section, ii) the calcium looping section (which includes the calciner, carbonator, and optional solid storage), iii) the CO₂ purification unit (CPU), iv) the air separation unit (ASU), and v) the heat recovery system based on solar salts loop with thermal energy storage (TES) and steam cycle. A solar salt system has been assumed for heat recovery, as proposed by Steinparzer et al. (2012, 2014) in order to efficiently recover the time-variable high temperature thermal power from the EAF flue gas and CaL system. Each of these subsystems is described in the following.

The first step involves cooling the EAF off-gas (stream #1) to a temperature suitable for the fan (≤ 400 °C), which injects the gases (stream #2) into the carbonator; therefore, the gas should be cooled when its temperature is higher than 400 °C. To achieve this, a gas cooler is placed between the EAF and the carbonator. Solar salts from the cold tank (stream #18) in the TES enter the gas cooler at 265 °C. The temperature of the heated solar salts at the outlet of the gas cooler (stream #19) is limited to 540 °C by adjusting their mass flow rate, according to the EAF off-gas inlet temperature and flow rate.

The cooled flue gases (stream #3) enter the adiabatic carbonator, a circulating fluidised bed reactor (CFB) operating at an average temperature of 620 °C. In the carbonator, a CaO-based solid sorbent selectively captures the CO₂ molecules from the gas phase via the heterogeneous, exothermic carbonation reaction (Eq. 1). The main products from the carbonator are the CO₂-lean gas stream obtained after removing CO₂ from the gas phase and carbonated solids containing the formed CaCO₃ and CaSO₄, as well as unreacted CaO and ash. They exit the carbonator as a gas-solid mixture and are subsequently separated in the carbonator's cyclone.

The CO₂-lean gases leaving the cyclone are directed to the carbonator's convective pass for heat recovery. Following heat recovery, a portion of the cooled CO₂-lean gas may be recirculated to the carbonator (stream #4) to maintain adequate fluidisation velocity (≥ 3 m/s) in the carbonator riser when the flow rate of the EAF off-gas is insufficient. The remaining gas (stream #5) is sent to a bag filter for solids removal and

downstream gas treatment systems (originally included in the hosting plant) before being released to the stack.

The solids from the carbonator have two possible destinations, depending on the plant configuration. For plant configurations with solid storage attached to the carbonator, the solids (stream #6) are directed to the storage vessel, which mixes with the existing solid inventory. The mixed solids are then sent to the calciner (stream #7) at a constant flow rate. Due to mixing in the storage vessel, the composition of stream #7 differs from that of stream #6. Conversely, in configurations without solid storage, the solids from the carbonator (stream #6) are transferred directly to the calciner. In this case, streams #6 and #7 are the same, as no storage vessel is present.

In the CFB calciner, the solid sorbent is regenerated by driving the decomposition of CaCO₃ into CaO and CO₂ via the endothermic calcination reaction (reverse reaction in Eq. 1). The high temperature required for complete CaCO₃ calcination is achieved by burning fuel with high-purity oxygen (95 vol.%), resulting in a CO₂-rich gas produced in the calciner (De Lena et al., 2017). Solids from the calciner (stream #8) can either be sent to a second storage vessel attached to the calciner (configuration with two solid storage vessels) or directly returned to the carbonator for a new CO₂ capture cycle. In all configurations, solids (stream #9) pass through a fluidised bed heat exchanger (FBHE), where their temperature is reduced before entering the carbonator. The outlet temperature of the solids from the FBHE is adjusted based on the CO₂ flow entering the carbonator, to ensure an average carbonator temperature of 620 °C. Due to the sorbent capacity decay caused by the cyclic carbonation-calcination and by sulphation (Grasa and Abanades, 2006; Sun et al., 2007), fresh limestone (stream #18) is injected into the calciner to maintain adequate sorbent activity levels. Likewise, solids are purged from the calciner (stream #19) to regulate the accumulation of ash, deactivated sorbent, and CaSO₄ in the loop.

In the CaL plant configurations investigated in this work, residual forestry biomass (stream #17), whose properties are reported in Table 2, is burned in the calciner to maintain an average reactor temperature of 920 °C. The biomass is combusted with a mixture (stream #14) of high-purity oxygen (stream #12) and recycled CO₂-rich gas (stream #13). This strategy enables the production of a gas stream with a high CO₂ concentration, simplifying subsequent CO₂ purification. The ASU produces liquid oxygen with a purity of 95 vol.% at a constant rate (stream #11). To accommodate variable oxygen demand in the calciner, a cryogenic tank is used to store the liquid oxygen at -182 °C and 1.2 bar (Hanak et al., 2017), enabling flexible oxygen supply based on calciner operational requirements. The liquid oxygen storing system is equipped with a vaporiser to supply gaseous oxygen to the calciner. The excess

Table 2
Properties of the residual forestry biomass used as fuel in the calciner (Saeed et al., 2023).

Properties	Value
Higher heating value [MJ/kg, dry basis]	20.54
<i>Proximate analysis [wt.%, dry basis]^a</i>	
Volatile matter	74.10
Fixed carbon	21.85
Ash	4.05
<i>Ultimate analysis [wt.%, dry basis]</i>	
Carbon	51.00
Hydrogen	5.80
Nitrogen	0.90
Sulphur	0.04
Oxygen	38.21
Ash	4.05

^a The moisture content was assumed as 10 % for simulations.

oxygen flow rate into the calciner (stream #12) is adjusted to control the residual oxygen concentration in the CO₂-rich gas (stream #15) to 3 vol.%. Similarly, the CO₂-rich gas recirculation (stream #13) is adjusted to limit the maximum reactor temperature—by keeping the oxygen concentration in the calciner oxidant below 40 vol.%—and the superficial gas velocity in the riser. Although a high temperature of stream #13 would reduce the calciner’s fuel consumption, it is limited to 400 °C to ensure stability of the fan reinjecting the gas stream into the calciner. The remaining CO₂-rich gas (stream #15) is sent to a gas holder after undergoing dust and water removal. Positioning a gas storage unit between the calciner and the CPU allows the later to be fed at a constant CO₂-rich gas flow rate (stream #16), thereby avoiding off-design operation, as well as equipment oversizing and potential compressors inefficiencies and instabilities when operating at very low load compared to design. In the CPU, the CO₂-rich gas undergoes a sequence of processes—including dehydration, purification (via distillation), compression and liquefaction—to produce a stream of CO₂ with a purity of 99.9 mol.% at 110 bar and 28 °C suitable for transport and storage (Magli et al., 2022).

Solar salts are used to recover the residual heat from the EAF off-gas, CO₂-lean gas from the carbonator, and CO₂-rich gas from the calciner. Consequently, a TES system is placed between the CaL section and the steam cycle, as shown in Fig. 2. The TES system consists of two tanks for storing cold and hot solar salts. Cold solar salts at 265 °C (streams #21, #23, #25, and #27) are sent to the different heat recovery devices in the CaL section at variable flow rates based on heat availability to produce hot solar salts at 540 °C, which are then stored in the hot tank (streams #22, #24, #26, and #28). In the steam cycle section, a stable flow of hot solar salt is supplied to an arrangement of shell-and-tube heat exchangers to produce superheated steam at 500 °C and 60 bar. The superheated steam is subsequently used to produce power in the steam turbine. More details about heat recovery and steam cycle are included in the **Supplementary material**. The produced power is used to drive the CO₂ capture plant (fans, ASU compressors, CPU compressors, and pumps), while any surplus electricity can either be supplied to the EAF plant to reduce steelmaking operational costs or exported to generate additional revenues for the integrated plant. The latter is assumed here to perform the economic analysis.

2.2.2. Flexibility strategies

Specific strategies are incorporated into the CaL plant to improve its flexibility in processing the fluctuating EAF off-gas. The plant components involved in these strategies are highlighted (dark grey) in the schematic shown in Fig. 2, with detailed descriptions provided in the following paragraphs.

- I. **Carbonator with variable fluidisation velocity and gas recirculation:** Because of the EAF off-gas flow rate variability, the carbonator must operate with a variable superficial gas velocity in the riser. Experiments conducted by Diego and Arias (2020) in a CaL pilot plant indicated that low gas velocities in the carbonator (2–3 m/s) might favour CO₂ capture efficiency due to higher sorbent inventories and residence times. However, excessively low gas velocities could compromise capture efficiency due to the low solid circulation rates between the carbonator and the calciner and unstable operation. Based on these findings, a minimum superficial gas velocity of 3 m/s is assumed for the carbonator riser. Considering the average carbonator temperature of 620 °C assumed in this work and the cross-section area of the reactor, a volumetric flow rate of 96 Am³/s is required to maintain the minimum superficial gas velocity. Therefore, for periods with lower EAF off-gas flow rates (Fig. 1), a portion of CO₂-lean gas exiting the carbonator is recirculated back to the reactor (stream #4 in Fig. 2). Although higher superficial gas velocities could be achieved through increased gas recirculation (or air injection), this would result in CO₂ dilution, thereby reducing the carbonator’s CO₂ capture efficiency. The cross-section area of the carbonator riser is determined by the maximum volumetric flow (225 Am³/s) and a superficial gas velocity of 7 m/s. Therefore, for periods with volumetric flow rates of EAF off-gas higher or equal to 96 Am³/s, no gas recirculation is required, and the gas velocity in the riser ranges between 3 m/s and 7 m/s, according to the flow rate entering the carbonator. A comparison of the profiles of the EAF off-gas and the gas stream effectively entering the carbonator is included in the **Supplementary material**.
- II. **Adiabatic carbonator + external fluidised bed heat exchanger (FBHE):** In standard CaL systems—designed to capture CO₂ from stable or

Fig. 2. Carbon capture plant scheme based on the CaL technology. Dashed lines are used for the contours of solid storage vessels to indicate that their presence is optional. **Abbreviations:** EAF: Electric arc furnace, CPU: CO₂ purification unit, ASU: Air separation unit, FBHE: Fluidised bed heat exchanger, TES: Thermal energy storage based on solar salts, HT: Hot tank, CT: Cold tank.

slightly variable flue gases—the carbonator is equipped with internal heat transfer surfaces to regulate the reactor’s temperature. Water or other heat transfer fluids absorb part of the thermal energy released during the carbonation reaction, ensuring the reactor maintains the desired temperature. The heat transfer system must handle both the sensible heat of solids arriving from the calciner (typically at $> 900\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) and the heat released by the exothermic carbonation reaction. Furthermore, effectively controlling the carbonation temperature is critical, as it significantly influences the CO_2 capture efficiency.

In the CaL plant applied to EAF steelmaking, the variability of EAF off-gas properties leads to the carbonator operating under variable conditions due to fluctuations in both the gas and solids input (sensible heat) and the heat released from the carbonation reaction. One potential strategy to facilitate the operation of the CFB reactor under variable load is incorporating an FBHE to control the temperature of solids entering the carbonator (Astolfi et al., 2019; Basu, 2015). Additionally, the FBHE can be designed to handle all the heat absorption required in the carbonator (externally, before the solids enter the reactor), enabling the implementation of an adiabatic carbonator without internal heat transfer surfaces (Criado et al., 2017). This design enhances system flexibility and control by decoupling heat extraction from the reacting capture process. In practice, the solids’ temperature at the carbonator inlet (FBHE outlet) can be controlled by regulating the bypass level of solids through the FBHE to keep an average carbonator temperature of $620\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. For simulations conducted in this work, the temperature of solids entering the carbonator is adjusted based on the energy balance of this reactor, considering the target carbonator temperature ($620\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) and properties of incoming EAF off-gas (temperature, flow rate, and CO_2 content).

III. *Intermediate solid storage*: Previous studies have investigated the inclusion of intermediate solids storage to enhance the flexibility of the CaL system to capture CO_2 from power plants flue gases with load changes. With this strategy, it is possible to decouple the calciner island (calciner, CPU and ASU) from EAF off-gas variability caused by power plant load changes (Criado et al., 2017). Additionally, solid storage allows the calciner to be fed with an average carbonated solid input, resulting in smaller calciner island components and, therefore, CAPEX savings (Astolfi et al., 2019, 2021). Similarly, solid storage can be employed to strategically adjust the calciner load (fuel and power demand) to optimise the system’s economic performance based on the electricity price (Hanak et al., 2016).

Intermediate solids storage between the carbonator and the calciner is included in this work to mitigate the impact of EAF off-gas variability on the calciner island operation. As described in Section 2.2.3, two plant configurations featuring one or two solid storages are analysed. In either configuration, solids with variable composition from the carbonator are stored before being sent to the calciner at a constant flow rate. Regenerated solids produced in the calciner can be sent directly to the carbonator (case with one solids storage) or temporally stored in a second vessel (case with two solids storage). The solids storage vessels are assumed to be fluidised to prevent agglomeration issues and promote rapid mixing with the solid inventory, thereby buffering fluctuations in the composition of solids entering the calciner; therefore, the calciner exhibits a more stable operation. From an energetic standpoint, operating the solids storage vessels at low superficial gas velocities—such those in the minimum fluidisation regime—is preferred since it limits the heat transferred from the solids bed to the fluidising gas, thereby limiting the impact on the calciner fuel demand. Similarly, high fluidising gas temperatures enhances the system’s overall energy efficiency. In this context, a portion of the EAF off gas can be employed to fluidise the solids storage vessel with solids from the carbonator, then this gas stream is recirculated to the carbonator (Kettunen and Rosnell, 2024). Likewise, steam could be used as the fluidising gas in the vessel receiving

solids from the calciner. A simplified energy balance on the fluidised solid vessels indicated that the calciner’s fuel consumption increases by approximately 15% ¹ due to heat transfer from solids to the fluidising gas. Nonetheless, the technical feasibility of fluidised storage vessels with the large solid inventories required to achieve the desired calciner’s operating stability must be confirmed through dedicated studies. Therefore, the detailed simulation of the solids storing vessel’s fluidisation and its impact on the overall system’s energy balance are not included in the current analysis.

IV. *Liquid Oxygen and CO_2 -rich gas storage*: Two fluid storage units are incorporated into the CaL plant to store the liquid oxygen from the ASU and CO_2 -rich gas from the calciner. These units buffer fluctuations in the calciner’s oxygen demand and CO_2 -rich gas production caused by variations in the composition of solids entering the calciner, enabling stable and full-load operation of the ASU and CPU. The ASU produces liquid oxygen at a constant rate, which may be stored in a cryogenic tank at $-182\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 1.2 bar. Liquid oxygen is extracted from the cryogenic tank, vaporised and supplied to the calciner at variable flow rates based on the thermal demand (fuel combustion) to maintain an average calciner temperature of $920\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Similarly, the variable CO_2 -rich gas produced in the calciner is stored in a gas storage unit at low pressure and temperature (i.e., 1 atm, $30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), after initial water removal and dust removal. The CPU processes a constant gas flow rate from the storage. Consequently, the ASU and CPU can be designed for average, stable loads.

V. *Thermal energy storage (TES) between the CaL reactors and the power block*: Heat recovery is critical for improving the energy efficiency of the CaL process. In the standard CaL plant configurations, heat recovery is performed using water to cool down the flue gases and produce superheated steam, which is then utilised in a steam cycle to generate power. Given the fluctuations in the heat sources—such as mass flow rate and temperature of gas and solid streams and heat extraction in the FBHE—in the current application, the heat recovery and power generation systems must be designed to operate flexibly. Based on experience from the concentrated solar power (CSP) sector, thermal energy storage (TES) can buffer the heat source fluctuations. This leads to the steam cycle operating under reduced variability or at constant load. At the commercial level, TES systems commonly employ either steam accumulators or molten salts (González-Roubaud et al., 2017). In steam accumulators, thermal energy is stored as pressurised hot water in a Ruth accumulator system. Saturated steam is then produced by gradually lowering the pressure (flashing) in the accumulator device from the nominal value to the minimum suitable pressure (temperature) to feed the turbine (Steinmann and Eck, 2006). Nonetheless, implementing steam accumulators in the CaL plant applied to EAF steelmaking will not avoid partial load operation of the steam cycle since steam is produced at variable pressure and temperature. In the case of the TES system with solar salts, storage tanks are used to store the solar salts. These tanks can be designed to receive the variable flow of hot solar salts from the heat sources and provide them to the steam cycle at a constant mass flow rate and temperature, similar to a CSP solar plant; therefore, superheated steam is generated at a stable load. Additionally, the high density of solar salts leads to reduced storage volume requirements. On the other hand, one key drawback of TES systems with solar salts is the relatively high solidification temperature, that determines a correspondingly high minimum operating temperature ($250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for most solar salts Pan et al., 2018).

In this work, a TES system using solar salts as the heat transfer fluid is employed to recover residual heat from EAF off-gas,

¹ Estimated with a fluidisation velocity of 0.1 m/s , a fluidising gas temperature at the inlet of $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and a temperature of solids entering the vessel of $620\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 3. Simplified schemes of the CaL section configuration for each case analysed. Dashed lines are for gas streams, dashed-dotted lines are for solid streams with variable flow rates, and solid lines are for solid streams with constant flow rates. Some components (e.g., reactors convective passes and fans) are omitted for simplicity. **NST-V:** CaL without solids storage and variable solid circulation, **NST-C:** CaL without solids storage and constant solid circulation, **1ST-C:** CaL with one solids storage vessel and constant solid circulation, **2ST:** CaL with two solids storage vessels.

carbonator flue gas, CO_2 -rich gas from the calciner, and solids in the FBHE (see Fig. 2).

2.2.3. CaL process design

As mentioned in Section 2.2.2, intermediate solid storages can be implemented to mitigate the impact of the variability of EAF flue gas on the calciner island operation. Typically, two solid storing vessels—one attached to each reactor—have been considered in previous studies (Criado et al., 2017; Hanak et al., 2016; Astolfi et al., 2019, 2021). However, alternative configurations, such as those with increased flow rates of solid circulated (no storage) or with a single storage vessel, can also be considered to limit the variability in the calciner island operation. Consequently, this work analyses and compares four different plant configurations from a techno-economic perspective. The distinction among these cases lies in the configuration of the CaL section, as presented in Fig. 3, while the other sections (CPU, ASU, TES, steam cycle, etc.) remain consistent across all cases.

Furthermore, the analysis assumes that the CO_2 capture efficiency in the carbonator is 95% of the maximum capture efficiency achievable as dictated by the equilibrium of the carbonation reaction. A minimum $F_{\text{Ca}}/F_{\text{CO}_2}$ molar ratio of 8 is considered during simulations, which is consistent with the assumed capture efficiency and the low sulphur content in the recirculated solids² (the maximum CaSO_4 -to- CaO molar ratio at

the carbonator inlet was 0.0003). Moreover, to achieve this capture efficiency, the carbonator's solid inventory must be maintained sufficiently high (e.g., around 1000 kg/m^2) by controlling the internal solid circulation (see Fig. 4c in Diego and Arias, 2020)

a) *Case NST-V:* In this case, presented in Fig. 3a, no intermediate solid storage is included in the simulated system. Therefore, the solids produced in the carbonator go directly to the calciner (and vice versa). During simulations, the flow of circulated solids between the reactors (external recirculation) is adjusted based on the CO_2 flow entering the carbonator with the EAF off-gas (Fig. 1c) and the energy balance to maintain its average operating temperature at 620°C , as follows: during periods with sufficiently high CO_2 intake, the heat released from the carbonation reaction is sufficient to maintain the target reactor temperature. In such cases, the solids flow rate into the carbonator is solely determined by considering a $F_{\text{Ca}}/F_{\text{CO}_2}$ ratio of 8, which is selected to achieve the desired CO_2 capture efficiency in the carbonator. If the heat released from the carbonation exceeds the requirement to keep the average reactor temperature at 620°C , the solids coming from the calciner are cooled in the FBHE.

Conversely, for periods with low CO_2 concentrations and EAF off-gas temperatures, the heat produced from the carbonation reaction is insufficient to maintain the target reactor temperature. Therefore, additional energy should be supplied as sensible heat by increasing

² Sulphur and ash contents of the calciner fuel (biomass) are low (see Table 2). Furthermore, sulphur presence in the carbonator was not considered since information about the sulphur content in the EAF off-gas was not available. However,

sulphur content in the EAF off-gas is expected to be low due to the addition of sulphur removal additives (e.g., lime, dolomite) and the low sulphur content of the scrap (Schrama et al., 2017).

the solids flow rate entering the carbonator (which results in higher F_{Ca}/F_{CO_2} molar ratios).

Based on the mass and energy balance of the CaL section, the solids mass flow rates exchanged between the reactors are in the range of 20–150 kg/s. However, with solid inventories of ~ 1000 kg/m² and superficial gas velocities of 3–7 m/s, higher entrained solids flow rates exit from the reactor risers. This means that only a portion of solids is effectively sent to the other reactor, while the remainder is recirculated internally. In practice, the internal/external solid recirculation flows can be controlled using dual loop-seals, which consist of two recycle chambers and their respective overflow channels. One of the overflow channels is connected to the same reactor while the other is connected to the other reactor. In this way, the fraction of solids recirculated internally and externally is controlled by regulating the superficial gas velocity in the corresponding recycle chamber (Bischi et al., 2013). In addition to dual loop-seals, advanced control technologies specifically developed for systems with strong cross-interacting process variables will be required. Examples of such control technologies are multivariable predictive control (MPC) based on state-space models of the controlled system (Findejs et al., 2009), and data-driven controls based on deep learning approaches (Han et al., 2025).

Additionally, in this case (NST-V), CO₂-rich gas is recirculated to the calciner for two purposes. First, it moderates the maximum combustion temperature by maintaining an oxygen concentration below or equal to 40 mol.% in the oxidant. Second, it is used to control the superficial gas velocity in the calciner's riser. Consequently, the CO₂ recirculation rate is increased to ensure a minimum superficial gas velocity in the calciner of 3 m/s during period with reduced load. While this strategy leads to increased fuel consumption, it allows the calciner to be kept under fast fluidisation conditions at each simulated point.

- b) *Case NST-C*: Similarly to case NST-V, the second case (Fig. 3b) does not include intermediate solid storage. However, in this configuration, the solids circulation from the calciner to the carbonator is maintained constant across all operating points. The constant solids flow rate is set to have an F_{Ca}/F_{CO_2} ratio of 8 based on the maximum CO₂ flow entering the carbonator. This implies that, for other points with lower CO₂ flows (F_{CO_2}), the F_{Ca}/F_{CO_2} ratio will be higher since the sorbent flow (F_{Ca}) remains constant. Moreover, solids cooling in the FBHE is required for all points because of the incremented flow rate of hot solids into the carbonator. With an increased, constant solid flow rate, the composition of the solids produced in the carbonator (i.e., the CaCO₃ content) presents less variability; therefore, it leads to a more stable operation of the calciner island compared to case NST-V. Consequently, this case represents a strategy to reduce fluctuations in the calciner island operation without increasing the CaL section complexity by including extra components (intermediate solid storage).
- c) *Case 1ST-C*: As depicted in Fig. 3c, this plant configuration includes one solid storage vessel that receives the solids produced in the carbonator. As in NST-C, the solid flow rate fed to the carbonator is maintained constant and is determined similarly to have an F_{Ca}/F_{CO_2} of 8 based on the maximum CO₂ flow rate entering the carbonator. In the solid storage vessel, which is kept fluidised, the incoming solids mix quickly with the existing solid inventory. As a result, the composition of solids at the storage outlet (calciner inlet) is more stable. As a consequence, the calciner capacity, fuel consumption and CAPEX are lower compared to the case without storage. For simplicity, the current analysis assumes instantaneous mixing of solids within the storing vessel. Additionally, the solid inventory is maintained constant by equalising the solids flow rate exiting the storage (to the calciner) with the incoming solids flow from the carbonator ($\dot{m}_{s,in} = \dot{m}_{s,out}$).
- d) *Case 2ST*: This case (Fig. 3d) includes two storage vessels to store solids exiting the carbonator and the calciner, respectively.

Both vessels are kept fluidised; hence, the assumption of instantaneous mixing also holds for this case. The flow rate and temperature of solids entering the carbonator are determined following the same approach used for NST-V. Therefore, the solids flow rate entering the carbonator is variable. The solids exiting the carbonator at a variable rate are sent to the first storage vessel and mixed with its solid inventory. This leads to a solid stream with a more uniform composition at the vessel outlet. The storage vessel is designed to supply the calciner with a constant solids flow rate, corresponding to the average flow calculated from the different solids flow rate values at the vessel's inlet. Therefore, as in 1ST-C case, the calciner operates with a constant solids input. However, compared to 1ST-C case, the calciner processes a lower solid flow rate, which implies smaller component sizes and reduced fuel and limestone consumption. The second storage vessel receives the nearly constant³ solid flow rate from the calciner and provides the carbonator with the required solids flow rate, according to the CO₂ input and the sensible heat required to maintain the carbonator temperature. Since the solids input and output in the solids storing vessels are different, the solids inventory in the vessels changes over time.

For the CaL plant applied to EAF steelmaking, the design and sizing of the components depend on several assumptions and goals. For example, the design point can be selected to either maximise the system performance (e.g., maximise the CO₂ capture efficiency or minimise the specific fuel consumption) or to guarantee a trade-off between technical and economic performances. In this work, the system is designed to achieve high CO₂ capture efficiencies in the carbonator, targeting values of $\sim 90\%$. Therefore, the plant components are designed based on the most critical conditions dictated by the EAF off-gas properties (e.g. maximum flow rate, maximum CO₂ concentration, etc.). The target is to assess and compare the four cases described above, while attaining high CO₂ capture rates. However, optimising the operating strategies of each plant configuration falls outside the scope of the present work. A detailed description of the design of the different components in the CaL plants is included in the **Supplementary material**, while a summary of the simulations parameters is provided in Table 3.

2.3. Simulation strategy

Simulations of the CO₂ capture plant were conducted using the EAF off-gas properties presented in Fig. 1 as inputs, including mass flow rate, composition, and temperature. 0D models for the different sections of the CaL plant were implemented based on the design specification outlined in Section 2.2.3. Each data point was assumed to represent a specific operating condition of the CO₂ capture plant. Accordingly, simulations for each point were performed to reproduce the mass and energy balances of the designed components under the different operational conditions defined by the profile of the EAF off-gas properties. Off-design operation was accounted for in the CaL reactors by adjusting the gas recirculation to maintain adequate fluidisation velocities and solid circulation based on the CO₂ flow and energy balance in the carbonator. Similarly, off-design calculations for heat recovery units were conducted by using built-in routines in the Thermoflex software. Nonetheless, it is important to note that the simulations were conducted assuming that each operating point is a quasi-steady state of the system. This means that the dynamic effects associated to the inertia of the CaL reactors and heat recovery sections were not included in the simulations.

For the CaL section, the model was implemented in Aspen Plus v14 to reproduce the mass and energy balances of the carbonator and calciner. The carbonator is modelled with a specified exit temperature of 620 °C.

³ Even though the calciner processes a constant solids flow rate, the amount of CaCO₃ to be calcined varies. Therefore, the flow rate and composition of the solids produced after calcination and the ash content from fuel combustion slightly vary over time.

The extent of the carbonation reaction was specified assuming to achieve 95% of the thermodynamic maximum CO₂ capture efficiency⁴. For each simulated point, the mass flow rate and temperature of calcined sorbent entering the carbonator was estimated according to the assumption of an adiabatic carbonator operating at 620 °C and a minimum F_{Ca}/FCO_2 ratio of 8.0.

The carbonation degree of the solids in the carbonator is calculated from the CO₂ molar balance (Eq. 2).

$$X_{ave} = \frac{F_{CO_2} \cdot E_{carb}}{F_{Ca}} \quad (2)$$

Where X_{ave} and E_{carb} are the average carbonation degree and carbonator CO₂ capture efficiency for each simulated point, respectively. Under the assumptions used in this study, the maximum carbonation degree of sorbent in the loop (X_{ave}) is 0.127 and 0.117 for cases with variable (NST-V and 2ST) and constant solid circulation (NST-C and 1ST-C), respectively, resulting in average carbonation levels of up to around 80% and involving feasible solid inventories for fast fluidised beds. A description of the carbonation degree and required sorbent inventory calculation is presented in the **Supplementary Material**.

Similarly, the calciner is modelled as an adiabatic reactor where the fuel input is adjusted to obtain an exit temperature of 920 °C. Full calcination of CaCO₃ and complete removal of SO₂ (originated from sulphur in biomass only) by CaO sulphation were assumed. Design specifications were implemented to adjust the flow rates of the recirculated CO₂-rich gas and oxygen so that the oxygen concentration at the calciner inlet, the superficial gas velocity, and the oxygen concentration at the calciner outlet are maintained at ≤40 vol.%, ≥3 m/s, and 3 vol.%, respectively.

The external FBHE was modelled in the Aspen Plus CaL model as a Heater block that removes a specified amount of heat from the solids stream, according to the design specification used for the mass flow rate and temperature of solids entering the adiabatic carbonator. For cases involving solid storage, where the solids in the vessel remain fluidised, a simplified model was developed to estimate the solid composition at each operational point by assuming instantaneous mixing of incoming solids with those already in the vessel. However, the model did not account for heat transfer from the storage vessel to its surroundings (heat losses) or the behaviour of the fluidised solid bed. The convective passes used to recover heat from the EAF off-gas, the carbonator's CO₂-lean gas, and the calciner's CO₂-rich gas were simulated in Thermoflex using its built-in component models. These units are initially sized during the design phase, and Thermoflex's built-in routines for off-design operation were subsequently used to estimate the production of solar salts at 540 °C based on the specified properties of the hot gases for each simulated point.

The CPU model is implemented in Aspen Plus following the assumptions and methods reported in Magli et al. (2022). Simulations were conducted by specifying the properties of the CO₂-rich gas from the gas holder, which are assumed to be the average properties of the fluctuating CO₂-rich gas entering the gas holder. Finally, the steam cycle was design with the Thermoflex software.

The main simulation parameters, which are common across all the cases are reported in Table 3

⁴ The calculations consist of the following main iterative steps: i) calculation of the EAF volumetric flow rate at 620 °C, ii) estimation of the CO₂-depleted gas recirculation required in the carbonator to maintain the superficial gas velocity above 3m/s, iii) calculation of the composition of the gas mixture effectively entering the carbonator (EAF flue gas + recycled gas), and iv) calculation of the resulting CO₂-depleted gas composition based on the 95% relative capture efficiency, which is the composition of the recirculated gas for the next operational point. The thermodynamic maximum capture efficiency is computed from the equilibrium CO₂ partial pressure calculated as $p_{CO_2,eq} [Pa] = 4.137 \times 10^{12} \cdot \exp(-20,474/T[K])$ (García-Labiano et al., 2002).

2.4. Thermodynamic analysis

This section describes the technical key performance indicators (KPIs) used to evaluate and compare the different CaL plant configurations. The analysis is based on average KPIs derived from the mass and energy balances produced for each simulated point of the CaL plant.

Since a portion of the CO₂-lean gas is recirculated to the carbonator during periods of low EAF flue gas flow, the average carbonator CO₂ capture efficiency is calculated by considering that the flue gas that enters the carbonator riser (and reacts with the solid sorbent) is the sum of the EAF off-gas and the recirculated CO₂-lean gas (Eq. 3).

$$E_{carb} = \frac{\dot{n}_{CO_2, carb-in} - \dot{n}_{CO_2, carb-out}}{\dot{n}_{CO_2, carb-in}} \quad (3)$$

Where E_{carb} is the average carbonator capture efficiency, $\dot{n}_{CO_2, carb-in}$ is the molar flow rate [kmol/s] of CO₂ entering the carbonator (with EAF off-gas + recirculated CO₂-lean gas), and $\dot{n}_{CO_2, carb-out}$ is the molar flow rate of CO₂ exiting the carbonator riser. Furthermore, the CO₂ capture efficiency referred to the CO₂ in the EAF off-gas ($E_{EAF\ off-gas}$) is calculated with Eq. 4.

$$E_{EAF\ off-gas} = \frac{\dot{n}_{CO_2, carb-in} - \dot{n}_{CO_2, carb-out}}{\dot{n}_{CO_2, EAF\ off-gas}} \quad (4)$$

Where $\dot{n}_{CO_2, EAF\ off-gas}$ is the average molar flow of CO₂ in the EAF off-gas entering the system.

The CO₂ capture rate (CCR_{CaL}) of the CaL plant is calculated to measure how much of the total CO₂ entering the system, including EAF off-gas, fuel, and fresh limestone, is sent to transport and storage from the CPU (Eq. 5).

$$CCR_{CaL} = \frac{\dot{n}_{CO_2, to-storage}}{\dot{n}_{CO_2, EAF\ off-gas} + \dot{n}_{CO_2, fuel} + \dot{n}_{CO_2, limestone}} \quad (5)$$

where $\dot{n}_{CO_2, to-storage}$ is the average molar flow rate of CO₂ produced in the CPU, $\dot{n}_{CO_2, fuel}$ is the average molar flow rate of CO₂ produced from fuel combustion, and $\dot{n}_{CO_2, limestone}$ is the average molar flow rate of CO₂ from the calcination of the fresh limestone injected as makeup.

Additionally, the different CaL plant configurations are compared based on their direct CO₂ emissions, which include CO₂ in the CO₂-lean gas sent to the stack and the CPU vent gas (Eq. 6).

$$\dot{m}_{CO_2, direct} = (1 - E_{EAF\ off-gas})\dot{m}_{CO_2, EAF\ gas} + (1 - CRR_{CPU}) \left[(\dot{m}_{CO_2, EAF\ gas} \times E_{carb}) - \dot{m}_{CO_2, solid\ loss} + \dot{m}_{CO_2, fuel} + \dot{m}_{CO_2, limestone} \right] \quad (6)$$

where $\dot{m}_{CO_2, solid-loss}$ (kg/s) is the mass flow of CO₂ in the solids losses in the carbonator cyclone and CRR_{CPU} is the CO₂ recovery rate of the CPU.

The specific fuel consumption of the CaL plant indicates how much fuel is consumed to capture one kilogram of CO₂; it can be calculated by considering the CO₂ captured from the EAF off-gas only (Eq. 7), or by considering the total CO₂ sent to storage, including that from fuel and limestone (Eq. 8).

$$SFC_1 = \frac{\dot{m}_{fuel} \times LHV_{fuel}}{\dot{m}_{CO_2, EAF\ off-gas} \times E_{EAF\ off-gas}} \quad (7)$$

$$SFC_2 = \frac{\dot{m}_{fuel} \times LHV_{fuel}}{\dot{m}_{CO_2, to-storage}} \quad (8)$$

Finally, the power balance of the CaL plant is conducted to calculate the net electric power that each plant configuration exports or imports (Eq. 9).

$$\dot{P}_{NET} = \dot{P}_{NET-SC} - \dot{P}_{AUX-CaL} - \dot{P}_{CPU} - \dot{P}_{ASU} \quad (9)$$

where \dot{P}_{NET-SC} is the net power output from the steam cycle, $\dot{P}_{AUX-CaL}$ includes all the electric auxiliaries in the CaL island (i.e., blowers, etc.), \dot{P}_{CPU} is the total electric power consumed by the CPU unit, and \dot{P}_{ASU} is the power consumed to produce and liquefy the oxygen required by the calciner

Table 3

Summary of the main simulation's parameters used in this work, which are consistent across all the simulated cases. The complete list and description of the parameters, including the design results obtained, are reported in **Supplementary information**.

Calcium Looping	
<i>Carbonator</i>	
Exit temperature, [° C]	620
F_{Ca}/F_{CO_2} , [mol/mol]	≥8
Superficial gas velocity, [m/s]	3.0 - 7.0
<i>Calcliner</i>	
Exit temperature, [° C]	920
Superficial gas velocity, [m/s]	3.0 - 7.0
O ₂ content at calcliner outlet, [mol.% wet basis]	3
Calcliner fuel	Residual forestry biomass (Table 2)
<i>CO₂ purification unit</i>	
Distillation column inlet pressure, [bar]	18
Minimum process temperature, [° C]	-53
Minimum ΔT in the cold box, [K]	3
Intercoolers outlet temperature, [° C]	28
CO ₂ delivery pressure, [bar]	110
Dehydration unit power consumption, [kWh _{el} /kg _{water}]	2.29
Blower isentropic efficiency, [%]	82
Compressors polytropic efficiency, [%]	77–80
<i>Air separation unit</i>	
O ₂ purity, [mol.%]	
Energy consumption, [kWh/t _{CO₂}]	638
LOX storage temperature, [° C]	-182
LOX storage pressure, [bar]	1.2
<i>Thermal energy storage</i>	
Heat transfer fluid	Solar salt (60 % NaNO ₃ , 40 % KNO ₃)
Hot tank temperature, [° C]	540
Cold tank temperature, [° C]	265
<i>Steam cycle</i>	
Superheated steam pressure, [bar]	60
Superheated steam temperature, [° C]	500
Condensing pressure, [bar]	0.043

2.5. Economic analysis

An economic analysis is performed to estimate the CAPEX and OPEX of the various CaL plant configurations. Additionally, the analysis considers the corresponding increment of steel cost and the cost of CO₂ avoidance (CCA). Finally, a sensitivity analysis is performed to evaluate the impact of key cost categories—namely CAPEX, carbon tax, biomass price, and CO₂ transport and storage—on the increment of steel cost. This analysis also serves to address the uncertainty typically associated with preliminary cost estimates for CO₂ capture plants based on CaL technology, which is under development and yet to reach full commercial maturity. The general assumptions used for the economic estimations are summarized in Table 4 and apply for all four plant configurations analysed.

The CAPEX was calculated as the sum of the Total Plant Cost (TPC) for each single component. Equipment cost estimations are derived using cost correlations, commercial software packages (e.g., Thermoflex), or scaling functions. The TPC was then computed by applying a set of factors to account for installation costs, process and project contingencies, owner's costs, and indirect costs (De Lena et al., 2019). A detailed description of the TPC estimation methodology is provided in the **Supplementary Information**.

After estimating the CAPEX and the OPEX, the project cash flow over the operational life was developed. The increment in steel cost is calculated as the additional cost (€ per ton of steel) that should be allocated to the produced steel to cover the expenses incurred from implementing the CO₂ capture project (hence, for decarbonizing steel). This value

corresponds to the break-even point where the Net Present Value (NPV) equals zero under the financial and cost assumptions from Table 4. Similarly, the cost of CO₂ avoidance (CCA) represents the break-even carbon tax (€/t_{CO₂}) that would allow the NPV of the project to be zero without generating an increment of steel cost. In other words, it represents the carbon tax value (constant throughout the project's lifetime) needed to make the CaL plant financially competitive with the unabated EAF plant. Since implementing the CO₂ capture project reduces the CO₂ emissions-related costs currently incurred by the EAF steelmaking plant under the Emission Trading System (Vu et al., 2022), a CCA lower than the carbon tax would make the scenario in which CaL-based CO₂ capture is implemented more economically competitive than the business-as-usual (i.e., continuing emitting while paying the CO₂ tax).

3. Results and discussion

In this section, the results obtained from the analysis are presented and discussed. It is important to remind that these results were obtained by assuming that each simulated point represents a quasi-steady state of the CaL system, as its dynamic response is not included in the simulations. While this represents a limitation of the current work, we believe that this simplification is an acceptable approximation for conducting a first techno-economic analysis of the proposed concepts and a comparison between different CaL configurations to understand the impact and potential of solid storages in terms of preliminary energy and mass balance performance and costs.

Table 4
Assumptions for the economic analysis of the CaL plant.

General economic conditions	Value	Reference
Currency	€ ₂₀₂₃	-
CaL plant capacity factor [%]	91.3	De Lena et al. (2019)
Tax rate [%]	30	Assumed for this work
Project lifetime [year]	25	De Lena et al. (2019)
Construction time of the CaL plant [year]	3	De Lena et al. (2019)
Percentage of TPC depreciated [%]	100	Assumed for this work
Discount rate [%]	8.0	Assumed for this work
Inflation [%]	3.0	Assumed for this work
CAPEX		
See section S4 in the Supplementary material	-	-
Fixed OPEX		
Insurance and local tax [% of TPC/year]	2.0	De Lena et al. (2019)
Maintenance cost [% of TPC/year]	2.5	De Lena et al. (2019)
Number of employees in the CaL plant	20	De Lena et al. (2019)
Cost of labour [€/year-person]	60,000	De Lena et al. (2019)
Maintenance labour [% of maintenance cost]	40	De Lena et al. (2019)
Administrative and support labour [% O&M labour cost]	30	De Lena et al. (2019)
Variable OPEX		
Residual forestry biomass price [€/GJ _{LHV, wet basis}] ^a	4.8	S2Biom Project (2017)
Limestone price [€/t _{limestone}]	15.0	Astolfi et al. (2019)
Electricity price [€/MWh] ^b	85	Eurostat (2025)
CO ₂ transport and storage cost [€/t _{CO2}]	30	Cremona et al. (2025)
Carbon tax [€/t _{CO2}] ^b	100	Mengden and Nieder (2025)
Carbon credit price [€/t _{CO2}] ^c	100	-

^a It is equivalent to 85 €/t_{biomass}.

^b Value representative for Norway

^c The carbon credit price is assumed equal to the carbon tax.

3.1. The impact of intermediate solid storage

Before analysing and discussing the technical and economic key performance indicators (KPIs) obtained for each of the four CaL plant configurations, an analysis on the impact of the two intermediate solids storage strategies on the performance of the calciner island is presented to ease the interpretation of the comparative analysis presented in the subsequent sections. For this purpose, the profiles of the CaCO₃ content at the outlet of the carbonator (red) and the inlet of the calciner (black) are depicted in Fig. 4 for cases (a) 1ST-C and (b) 2ST. Moreover, it should be noted that the red curve in Fig. 4 also represents the profile of CaCO₃ content in the solids entering the calciner for cases without intermediate solid storage, a) for NST-C and b) for NST-V.

The CaCO₃ content profiles at the inlet of the calciner (or outlet of the storage vessel receiving solids from the carbonator) were obtained with solid inventories in the storage vessels of 1750 tons and 750 tons for 1ST-C and 2ST, respectively. In the 1ST-C case, the solid inventory was defined to limit the variability of the superficial gas velocity in the calciner. With this solid inventory in the vessel, the minimum superficial gas velocity (4 m/s) in the calciner riser is 80.% of the on-design value (5 m/s). In contrast, the solid inventory defined for 2ST enables the calciner to operate at a constant superficial gas velocity of 5 m/s. While the selected solid inventories resulted in more stable calciner operation in both cases, the optimal solid inventories should be determined through an optimization analysis considering factors such as size limitations of the fluidised solid storage, fluidisation power consumption, and eco-

Fig. 4. Profiles of CaCO₃ composition in the solid stream exiting the carbonator (red) and in the solid stream exiting the vessel storing solids from the carbonator (black): a) Case with one solid storage and constant solid circulation (1ST-C), with a solid inventory of 1750 tons; b) Case with two solid storages (2ST), with a solid inventory of 750 tons for the storage vessel receiving solids from the carbonator. A reduced solid inventory of 100 tons is defined for the storage vessel receiving solids from the calciner since no buffering effect is required. Each operating point is related to a system simulation where corresponding values from Fig. 1 are used as inputs. The red line also represents the profile of CaCO₃ content in the solids entering the calciner for cases without intermediate solid storage: a) for NST-C and b) for NST-V.

Fig. 5. Profiles of relevant operating parameters of the calciner: a) Fuel input [MW_{th}], b) Calciner oxygen consumption [kg/s], and c) CO_2 -rich gas to CPU gas storage [kg/s]. Legends: NST-V: No solid storage, variable solid circulation between the CaL reactors, NST-C: No solid storage, constant solid circulation between the CaL reactors, 1ST-C: One solid storage, constant solid circulation between the CaL reactors, 2ST: Two solid storages. Each operating point corresponds to a system simulation where corresponding values from Fig. 1 are used as inputs.

conomic performance. Such an optimisation analysis is beyond the scope of the current analysis.

The variability in the composition of solids was significantly reduced in both cases due to the buffering effect of the solid inventory in the storage vessels. For 1ST-C (Fig. 4a), the solids entering the calciner exhibit a more stable CaCO_3 content than those produced in the carbonator. The CaCO_3 content at the storage vessel inlet fluctuates between 0.00 and 0.19 g/g (red curve), while it ranges from 0.03 to 0.07 g/g at the outlet, with an inventory of 1750 tons. Since the total solids flow rate supplied from the storage vessel to the calciner is maintained nearly constant at approximately 150 kg/s, the reduction in the maximum CaCO_3 content (0.07 vs 0.19 g/g) also reduces the peak load of the calciner (fuel input required for calcination), leading to a smaller, cheaper and more efficient calciner.

Similarly, in case 2ST (Fig. 4b), the solids entering the calciner exhibit a less variable CaCO_3 content (0.09–0.16 g/g) compared to the solids stream produced in the carbonator (0.00–0.20 g/g). The solids processing capacity of the calciner is about one-third for 2ST (54 kg/s), compared to the one required for 1ST-C (~150 kg/s). That means that the 2ST case requires a smaller calcination reactor fuel input. The lower

variability of CaCO_3 concentrations for 1ST-C are explained by the higher solid mass flow rate at the outlet of the storage vessel and the greater solid inventory, when compared to 2ST. The total mass of CaCO_3 from the carbonator is identical in both cases as the CO_2 capture efficiency is assumed to be the same (95% of the capture efficiency if the CO_2 equilibrium is reached) in both cases.

Three key parameters are used to analyse the calciner operation across the simulated CaL plant configurations: fuel power input, oxygen consumption, and the CO_2 -rich gas mass flow rate. As shown in Fig. 5a, the case NST-V (no storage and variable solid recirculation) resulted in the severest variability in the calciner fuel demand, although its fuel consumption is always lower than the NST-C configuration. In the cases without storage, since the solids processed in the calciner have a fluctuating mass flow rate and composition, the thermal input must be adjusted accordingly to maintain the calciner temperature at the target value of 920 °C. As a result, the calciner's thermal input of NST-V case ranged from 25 to 153 MW, with an average value of 46 MW. This implies that, in NST-V, the calciner must operate at a minimum thermal partial load of 16%. When the solid circulation between reactors is increased and kept constant (NST-C configuration), fluctuations in the calciner's thermal input are reduced. In this setup, the calciner processes a constant solids flow rate, meaning that the thermal input variability is solely driven by fluctuations in solids compositions, which result from the variable CO_2 capture in the carbonator. As a result, the calciner's minimum thermal power input increases significantly to 72 MW, compared to NST-V. Thus, the minimum thermal load in the calciner is 45% of the design load. Moreover, the average thermal power input for NST-C nearly doubles that of NST-V (90 MW vs. 46 MW). This higher fuel consumption results from the high solid recirculation between the reactors, set at 150 kg/s, based on the maximum CO_2 flow rate entering the carbonator and the targeted $F_{\text{Ca}}/F_{\text{CO}_2}$ molar ratio of 8. Additionally, in this configuration, a minimum superficial gas velocity of 3.1 m/s is maintained in the calciner's riser without requiring an increase in CO_2 -rich gas recirculation, as was necessary for NST-V.

The 1ST-C and 2ST configurations significantly reduce the calciner capacity due to the buffering effect of the solid storage on the solids' flow rate and composition. The calciner's thermal input fluctuates between 83–105 MW for 1ST-C and 39–49 MW for 2ST, with a minimum thermal partial load of 80% in both cases. Beyond stabilising calciner operation, the intermediate solid storage also lowers the calciner's design capacity, reducing investment costs for the calciner island.

As expected, the oxygen demand and CO_2 -rich gas flow rate (Fig. 5a and b, respectively) closely follow the calciner fuel input profile in each case. This is explained by the interdependency between oxygen consumption, CO_2 -rich gas production and fuel consumption rate. Since the reactor temperature and oxygen content at the outlet remain constant, both oxygen demand and CO_2 -rich gas production scale proportionally with the fuel input. Consequently, if calciner efficiency is maintained, the ratio between CO_2 released from CaCO_3 calcination and the required O_2 and fuel input remains constant.

Furthermore, integrating intermediate solid storage has a strong impact on the volume required to store the CO_2 -rich gas produced in the calciner. For plant configurations without solid storage, the CO_2 -rich gas holder volumes are 53,000 m^3 (NST-V) and 44,000 m^3 (NST-C). In contrast, with solid storage, the required volumes decrease to 22,000 m^3 for 1ST-C and 15,000 m^3 for 2ST.

3.2. Technical KPIs

Simulations were performed to obtain the mass and energy balances of each plant configuration, using the EAF off-gas properties shown in Fig. 1 as inputs. The results from each simulated operating point were then used to calculate the average values of key technical KPIs, which are reported in Table 5.

Fig. 6. Sankey diagram of the CO₂ flows [t/h] in the different CaL plant's configurations. "Carb. solids loss" corresponds to the CO₂ contained in the solid CaCO₃ recovered in the fabric filter treating the gases exiting the carbonator's convective pass.

3.2.1. Material balance

Cases NST-C and 1ST-C resulted in the largest consumption of fuel, fresh limestone, and oxygen, nearly doubling the values obtained in NST-V and 2ST. This outcome is explained by the higher solids flow rate treated by the calciner—approximately three times that of NST-V and 2ST (150 kg/s vs 54 kg/s). Since the assumption of 95% relative CO₂ capture efficiency in the carbonator is consistent across all four cases, the carbonator capture efficiency remains the same (91.26%) and thus, the amount of CaCO₃ processed in the calciner is also unchanged. Therefore, the higher average thermal input for NST-C and 1ST-C is attributed to the additional energy required to heat the solids stream entering the calciner from 620 °C to 920 °C. When comparing NST-V and 2ST, the calciner processes the same average amount of solids; however, the fuel consumption of NST-V is slightly higher (46.2 MW_{th} vs. 43.7 MW_{th}) due to the increased CO₂-rich gas recirculation required to maintain the fluidisation velocity above 3 m/s in the calciner riser. Since the recirculated CO₂-rich gas stream enters the calciner at 400 °C, additional energy is required to heat it up to the calciner's operating temperature of 920 °C. In contrast, 2ST-V does not require such an increase in CO₂-rich gas recirculation thanks to the buffering effect of the solid storage on the variability of the calciner operation.

Even though the CO₂ input from the EAF off-gas (11.52 t/h) and the CO₂ capture in the carbonator (10.51 t/h) are the same, the higher fuel and limestone consumption in NST-C and 1ST-C resulted in higher flow rates of CO₂ processed by the CPU and sent to storage (~43 t/h) compared to NST-V and 2ST (~26 t/h). However, there were no significant differences in the CPU's CO₂ recovery rates (94.36% - 95.23%) or the CaL CO₂ capture rates (91.02% - 92.56%).

Based on specific fuel consumption, cases with constant solid circulation between the reactors (NST-C and 1ST-C) were less energy efficient in capturing CO₂. Their specific fuel consumptions (relative to the total CO₂ captured) are between 19% and 22% higher than those of NST-V

and 2ST. Referring to the CO₂ captured from the EAF off-gas (SFC₁), NST-C and 1ST-C consumed 95% to 107% more fuel per kg of CO₂, compared to NST-V and 2ST. Nevertheless, the higher fuel consumption led to a greater carbon removal rate (a more negative atmospheric CO₂ balance) for NST-C and 1ST-C, assuming the CO₂ from the fuel is biogenic.

The average CO₂ flows rates (t/h) between the sections for the different CaL plant configurations are graphically represented in Fig. 6, where it is evident that, compared to NST-V and 2ST, cases with constant solid circulation (NST-C and 1ST-C) generate approximately twice the amount of CO₂ from fuel combustion to capture the same quantity of CO₂ from the EAF off-gas. Moreover, the figure shows that the larger CO₂ flow rate treated by the CPU—and consequently, the higher CO₂ losses through the CPU vent gas—is the main contributor to the increased direct emissions reported in Table 5 for cases NST-C and 1ST-C.

3.2.2. Power balance

As expected, the power produced by the steam cycle was higher in NST-C and 1ST-C due to the increased thermal input in the calciner. This higher thermal power is absorbed by the solar salts from the CO₂-rich gas stream and solids in the external FBHE. Regarding the power consumption in the CaL section, it was higher in cases with intermediate solid storage due to the power required to keep the solid storage fluidised. The power consumption for fluidising the solid storage was estimated at 2.4 MW_e and 1.2 MW_e for 1ST-C and 2ST, respectively. When comparing 1ST-C against NST-C, the increase in power consumption in the CaL section is 87.4%. Similarly, 2ST requires 40.4% more power for the CaL section than NST-V.

The power consumption of the CPU is primarily driven by the CO₂ flow rate produced by the unit. Consequently, the CPU power consumption for NST-C and 1ST-C is 67.5% to 100% higher than NST-V and 2ST. Similarly, the power consumed by the ASU is directly related to the oxy-

Table 5

Average technical KPIs for each CaL plant configuration analysed (Legends: **NST-V**: No solid storage, variable solid circulation, **NST-C**: No solid storage, constant solid circulation, **1ST-C**: One solid storage, constant solid circulation, **2ST**: Two solid storages.).

KPI	NST-V	NST-C	1ST-C	2ST
Fuel consumption (calcliner), [MW _{th}]	46.2	90.3	90.3	43.7
Oxygen consumption, [t/h]	13.8	26.8	26.8	13.1
Fresh limestone consumption, [t/h]	3.1	9.5	9.5	3.9
<i>Captured CO₂ balance</i>				
CO ₂ from EAF off-gas, [t/h]-[%] ^a	10.5 (38.0)	10.5 (23.1)	10.5 (23.1)	10.5 (39.1)
CO ₂ from fuel (biogenic), [t/h]-[%] ^a	15.8 (57.1)	30.8 (67.8)	30.8 (67.8)	14.9 (55.5)
CO ₂ from CaCO ₃ make-up, [t/h]-[%] ^a	1.4 (4.9)	4.2 (9.2)	4.2 (9.2)	1.5 (5.4)
CO ₂ captured in CaL section, [t/h]	27.7	45.5	45.5	26.9
Capture efficiency - $E_{carb}(E_{EAF,off-gas})$, [%]	91.3 (87.4)	91.3 (87.4)	91.3 (87.4)	91.3 (87.4)
CPU CO ₂ recovery rate- CCR_{CPU} , [%]	94.4	94.5	94.8	95.2
CO ₂ capture rate - CCR_{CaL} , [%]	91.0	92.4	92.7	91.7
CO ₂ sent to storage from CPU, [t/h]	26.0	42.9	43.1	25.5
Direct CO ₂ emissions - $\dot{m}_{CO_2,direct}$, [t/h]	2.6	3.6	3.4	2.3
Specific fuel consumption - $SFC_2(SFC_1)$, [MJ/kg _{CO2}]	6.0 (15.8)	7.1 (30.9)	7.1 (30.9)	5.9 (15.0)
Atmospheric net CO ₂ balance, [t/h] ^b	-13.4	-27.3	-27.5	-12.6
<i>CaL plant power balance</i>				
Steam cycle net power output - \dot{P}_{NET-SC} , [MW]	16.7	29.5	29.5	16.3
CaL power consumption - $\dot{P}_{AUX-CaL}$, [MW]-[%] ^c	2.8 (18.4)	3.0 (11.5)	5.7 (19.6)	3.9 (24.7)
CPU power consumption - \dot{P}_{CPU} , [MW]-[%] ^c	3.7 (24.1)	6.0 (23.1)	6.2 (21.3)	3.6 (22.6)
ASU power consumption - \dot{P}_{ASU} , [MW]-[%] ^c	8.8 (57.5)	17.1 (65.4)	17.1 (59.2)	-8.4 (52.6)
CaL plant net power output - \dot{P}_{NET} , [MW]	1.3	3.3	0.6	0.4
<i>CaL specific KPIs relative to the steel produced in the EAF plant</i>				
Fuel consumption, [MWh _{LHV} /t _{steel}]	0.4	0.8	0.81	0.39
CaCO ₃ consumption, [t _{limestone} /t _{steel}]	0.028	0.085	0.085	0.029
CO ₂ emissions from EAF off-gas avoided [t _{CO2} /t _{steel}]	0.094	0.094	0.094	0.094
CO ₂ to storage, [t _{CO2} /t _{steel}]	0.233	0.383	0.384	0.228
CO ₂ direct emissions (from carbonator and CPU), [t _{CO2} /t _{steel}]	0.023	0.031	0.030	0.020
CO ₂ removed, [t _{CO2} /t _{steel}] ^b	-0.118	-0.244	-0.245	-0.113

^a percent of the total CO₂ captured, from EAF off-gas + fuel + fresh limestone.

^b negative values were obtained since the CO₂ from biomass burnt in the calciner is removed from the atmosphere. The atmospheric CO₂ balance does not consider emissions derived from biomass processing and transport or land use change.

^c share in the total power consumption of the CaL plant.

Table 6

Total Plant Cost (TPC) breakdown for the four cases analysed (Legends: **NST-V**: No solid storage, variable solid circulation, **NST-C**: No solid storage, constant solid circulation, **1ST-C**: One solid storage, constant solid circulation, **2ST**: Two solid storages).

Item	NST-V	NST-C	1ST-C	2ST
CaL section, [M€] - [%]	108.0 (45.6)	108.0 (39.9)	101.6 (41.2)	90.2 (46.8)
EAF gas cooler, [M€]	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0
Carbonator, [M€]	41.2	41.1	41.1	41.1
FBHE, [M€]	15.2	15.2	15.2	15.2
Calcliner, [M€]	41.7	41.7	31.3	19.3
Solid storage, [M€]	-	-	4.1	4.7
CPU, [M€] - [%]	66.0 (27.9)	69.6 (25.8)	55.3 (22.5)	43.1 (22.3)
Baghouse filter, [M€]	2.9	2.9	2.4	1.6
Heat rejection, [M€]	2.8	2.7	2.7	2.8
Compressors, [M€]	26.2	33.7	34.1	26.5
Dehydration unit, [M€]	0.8	1.0	1.0	0.8
Gas holder, [M€]	32.3	28.0	13.8	10.3
Others, [M€]	1.0	1.3	1.3	1.0
ASU, [M€] - [%]	39.9 (16.8)	61.1 (22.6)	61.0 (24.8)	39.7 (20.6)
SC & TES, [M€] - [%]	23.1 (9.7)	31.5 (11.7)	28.4 (11.5)	19.9 (10.3)
TES, [M€]	4.6	5.4	2.3	3.2
SC, [M€]	18.5	26.1	26.1	16.8
Total Plant Cost, M€	237.0	270.3	246.4	192.9
	Baseline	+14%	+4%	-18.6%

Fig. 7. Breakdown of the increment in steel cost for the different cases assessed, with respect to an unabated plant subjected to the payment of the carbon tax. It represents the increment in the price of steel needed to cover the expenses generated from the application of the CaL CO₂ capture project. **Note:** The category “Others” encompasses a set of different expenditures, namely workforce (25%), maintenance (32%), insurance (25%), and taxes (18%). **Labels:** NST-V: No solid storage, variable solid circulation, NST-C: No solid storage, constant solid circulation, 1ST-C: One solid storage, constant solid circulation, 2ST: Two solid storages.

gen demand in the calciner. Thus, cases with constant solid circulation between the CaL reactors doubled the ASU power consumption. Furthermore, the ASU accounted for 53% to 65% of the total power consumed in the CaL plants. This significant share is due to high power consumption to produce liquid oxygen. This is the main driver for the low net power that can be exported from the CaL plant in each case. For plant configurations without intermediate solid storage (NST-V, NST-C), the exported power is 8%-11% of the net power produced by the steam cycle, while it drops to 1.9%-2.4% for cases with intermediate solid storage (1ST-C, 2ST) due to the additional power consumed to fluidise the storage’s solids bed.

3.2.3. KPIs for the steelmaking system

Regarding the specific fuel consumption relative to the steel produced by the EAF plant (MWh_{LHV}/t_{steel}), as expected, cases with constant solid circulation (NST-C and 1ST-C) exhibited higher values, reaching $0.81 MWh_{LHV}/t_{steel}$, compared to $0.40 MWh_{LHV}/t_{steel}$ for the NST-V and 2ST cases. For reference, the EAF steelmaking plant hosting the CaL system has a specific electricity consumption in the range of $0.45-0.63 MWh_e/t_{steel}$.

It is worth noting that the use of residual forestry biomass in the CaL plant provides a three-fold benefit. First, low-carbon steel is produced due to a substantial reduction in the direct CO₂ emissions (scope 1) of the hosting EAF plant—from $0.10 t_{CO_2}/t_{steel}$ ⁵ to $0.02-0.03 t_{CO_2}/t_{steel}$. Second, the electricity required for CO₂ capture, purification, and compression is fully self-generated, with surplus power available for export.

⁵ It corresponds to the direct emissions of the EAF plant where no abatement system is implemented to reduce the CO₂ emissions. It calculated as $11.52 t_{CO_2}/h \div 112 t_{steel}/h$ based on the measurements obtained for the EAF plant considered in this work.

Fig. 8. Breakdown of the cost of CO₂ avoided (CCA) for the different cases assessed. It represents the amount of money expended for each ton of CO₂ captured from the EAF off-gas. **Note 1:** CCA corresponds to the break-even carbon tax, leading to an NPV of the project equal to zero and with no increment in steel cost. **Note 2:** The category “Others” encompasses a set of different expenditures, namely workforce (25%), maintenance (32%), insurance (25%), and taxes (18%). **Labels:** NST-V: No solid storage, variable solid circulation between the CaL reactors, NST-C: No solid storage, constant solid circulation between the CaL reactors, 1ST-C: One solid storage, constant solid circulation between the CaL reactors, 2ST: Two solid storages.

Finally, as shown in Table 5, between 0.11 and 0.25 t_{CO_2}/t_{steel} can be removed from the atmosphere though the capture of biogenic CO₂ from the biomass combustion.

The specific limestone (t_{CaCO_3}/t_{steel}) consumption in the CaL plant is equivalent to 68% (NST-V and 2ST) and 207% (NST-C and 1ST-C) of the limestone consumed in the EAF steelmaking process. These numbers were obtained by considering the average specific CaO consumption in the EAF of $0.023 t_{CaO}/t_{steel}$.

3.3. Economic KPIs

The Total Plant Cost (TPC) breakdown for the four analysed cases is shown in Table 6 and it ranges from 193 M€ (2ST) to 270 M€ (NST-C). The CaL section accounts for the largest share of the CaL plant TPC (40%-47%), followed by the CPU (22%-28%) and the ASU (17%-25%). As expected, cases with constant solid circulation (NST-C and 1ST-C) resulted in the highest TPCs due to the larger capacities of components required for these plant configurations (Table 5), which is also reflected in greater amounts of CO₂ sent to storage. Using NST-V as a baseline, the TPC increased by 14% for NST-C. However, for 1ST-C, the increase was only 4%, thanks to the cost-reducing effect of solid storage on the CaL section and CPU. Likewise, 2ST resulted in the lowest TPC, which is 18.6%, 29%, and 22% lower than NST-V, NST-C, and 1ST-C, respectively.

In the CaL section, the CAPEX is dominated by the reactors, which account for 70%-77% of the section’s TPC, while the FBHE contributes 14%-18%. The inclusion of intermediate solid storage significantly reduces the calciner’s size and cost. Furthermore, the estimated costs of the solid storage systems (4 M€ for 1ST-C and 5 M€ for 2ST) are more than offset by the reduction in the calciner cost—11 M€ when comparing 1ST-C vs. NST-C and 23 M€ when comparing 2ST vs. NST-V. In

Fig. 9. Increment in steel cost as a function of a) CAPEX change, b) carbon tax, c) biomass price, d) CO₂ transport and storage cost, and e) CaL plant capacity factor. **Note:** The sensitivity analyses were conducted by varying the parameter in the x-axis of each subplot only, while the values for other parameters were not changed: Total CAPEX as reported in Table 6, carbon tax of 100 €/t_{CO₂}, biomass price of 85 €/t_{biomass}, CO₂ transport and storage cost of 30 €/t_{CO₂}, and CaL plant capacity factor of 91.3%. **Legends:** NST-V: No solid storage, variable solid circulation, NST-C: No solid storage, constant solid circulation, 1ST-C: One solid storage, constant solid circulation, 2ST: Two solid storages.

the CPU, the gas holder for storing CO₂-rich gas accounts for a significant share of the CPU's TPC. In NST-V, its cost share exceeds that of the compressor train (49% vs 40%) due to the large volume required to accommodate the highly fluctuating gas flow rate coming from the calciner while supplying the compressors with a constant gas flow rate. Moreover, implementing intermediate solid storage resulted in a significant reduction of the cost of the gas holder, driving down the CPU's TPC in 1ST-C and 2ST. The steam cycle has a higher cost in the cases with constant solid circulation due to the larger power output, which is consistent with the larger fuel consumption in the calciner.

3.3.1. Increment of steel cost

Fig. 7 presents the increment of steel cost for the analysed cases, along with its breakdown. In all cases, CAPEX and fuel are the main single categories contributing to the steel cost increase. Consequently, cases with the highest CAPEX and fuel consumption (NST-C and 1ST-C) show the highest increments of steel cost. Conversely, carbon credit revenues—generated from biogenic CO₂ capture produced by biomass combustion in the calciner—help to partly offset the impact of higher CAPEX and OPEX. Therefore, the higher fuel consumptions of NST-C and 1ST-C explain the slightly higher increment in steel cost in these cases (9% and 3%, respectively) when compared to the baseline (NST-V). Among all cases, 2ST case achieved the lowest increment of steel cost (26 €/t_{steel}) due to the reduced CAPEX and OPEX. The contribution from

the carbon tax category is the same for all the cases ($-9 \text{ €/t}_{\text{steel}}$) since the amount of CO_2 captured from the EAF off-gas, and thus the avoided carbon tax, remains the same under the assumptions considered in this work. Notably, the estimated increments of steel cost ($26 \text{ €/t}_{\text{steel}} - 36 \text{ €/t}_{\text{steel}}$) represent 6%–9% of the global average levelized cost of steel produced via the scrap-based EAF route, based on the data reported in IEA (2020).

3.3.2. Cost of CO_2 avoided (CCA)

Fig. 8 presents the Cost of CO_2 Avoided (CCA) and the breakdown into its contributing factors. It ranges between 202 and 255 €/t_{CO_2} . Despite the highest CAPEX and OPEX, NST-C and 1ST-C achieved the lowest CCA values at 208 €/t_{CO_2} and 202 €/t_{CO_2} , respectively. This is primarily due to the higher carbon credits revenues generated in these cases due to the negative emissions achieved—the value of the carbon credits is assumed to be equal to the CCA (carbon tax). However, two key considerations should be noted:

- i. The analysis assumes that the residual forestry biomass supply chain operated with 100% carbon efficiency, meaning all biogenic CO_2 in the biomass is effectively removed from the atmosphere. However, if the carbon balance of the biomass supply chain is considered—including potential land use change impacts—the benefits of higher biomass consumption could diminish due to a lower net generation of carbon credits. However, these factors are beyond the scope of the current analysis.
- ii. Burning more biomass in the calciner reduces resource efficiency, as it requires more fuel to capture the same amount of CO_2 from the EAF off-gas, while the availability of biomass for other uses (e.g., energy purposes) could be limited.

3.3.3. Sensitivity analysis

Sensitivity analyses were conducted to evaluate the variability of the increment in steel cost in response to changes in CAPEX ($-50\% - +50\%$), carbon tax ($0 - 250 \text{ €/t}_{\text{CO}_2}$), biomass price ($50 - 120 \text{ €/t}_{\text{biomass}}$), and CO_2 transportation and storage cost ($10 - 50 \text{ €/t}_{\text{CO}_2}$). As shown in Fig. 9a, 2ST consistently resulted in the lowest increment of steel cost across the CAPEX variation's range. Additionally, the estimations indicate that the increase in the CAPEX leads to a greater difference in the required increment of steel cost among the different cases to achieve an NPV equal to zero. This suggests that if higher plant costs are expected, 2ST becomes increasingly attractive compared to the other cases.

Fig. 9b shows that higher carbon tax values reduce the increment of steel cost, as greater revenues are generated from carbon credits and savings from the CO_2 emission reduction. Cases NST-C and 1ST-C exhibit a greater sensitivity to the carbon tax, as indicated by their steeper slopes. This is primarily due to their higher fuel consumption, which results in increased biogenic CO_2 capture—and consequently, greater CO_2 removal. When the carbon tax exceeds 160 €/t_{CO_2} for 1ST-C and 175 €/t_{CO_2} for NST-C, their respective increment in steel cost becomes lower than that of 2ST. 1ST-C requires the lowest carbon tax—200 €/t_{CO_2} —to achieve a zero increment in steel cost, thereby making the implementation of the CaL-based CO_2 capture project economically competitive. Conversely, higher biomass and CO_2 transport and storage (CO_2 T&S) costs lead to higher increments of steel costs. Like the carbon tax analysis, break-even points exist where the ranking of some cases shifts. However, within the considered biomass and CO_2 T&S ranges, 2ST consistently maintains the lowest increment in steel cost. Fig. 9e indicates that the increment of steel cost should be increased by 25%–30% when the CaL plant capacity factor is reduced from 91.3% to 50%. Furthermore, the slopes of the curves in Fig. 9(a–d) suggest that 2ST is less sensitive to parameter variations, which may indicate lower financial risk in the face of price volatility compared to NST-C and 1ST-C.

4. Conclusions

This work analysed and compared the techno-economic performance of four configurations of the CaL technology for capturing CO_2 from the fluctuating flue gases generated from an EAF steelmaking plant with capacity of 112 $\text{t}_{\text{steel}}/\text{h}$ and direct emissions (scope 1) of 11.52 $\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2}/\text{h}$. The analysis was performed by assuming a sequence of quasi-steady state operational points and process modelling and simulations were performed. The four configurations were defined based on the solids circulation strategy (variable or constant) and the inclusion of intermediate solids storage, as follows: no intermediate solids storage and variable solids circulation (NST-V), no intermediate solids storage and constant solids circulation (NST-C), one intermediate solids storage and constant solids circulation (1ST-C), and two solids storages (2ST).

The main findings of this work are summarized in the following conclusions:

- The strategy adopted for solids circulation between the reactors significantly influenced the calciner's fuel consumption and the related capacity and CAPEX of the calciner island (i.e., calciner reactor, ASU, and CPU). While constant solids recirculation (NST-C, 1ST-C) helped reduce the variability of solids composition and fuel demand in the calciner, the high solids flow rate processed by the calciner led to increased fuel demand. Conversely, regulating the sorbent feed to the carbonator in response to CO_2 input (variable solid circulation, NST-V, 2ST) proved more energy efficient, yielding lower absolute fuel consumptions ($\sim 45 \text{ MW}_{\text{th}}$ vs $90 \text{ MW}_{\text{th}}$) and specific fuel consumption ($\sim 6.0 \text{ MJ/kg}_{\text{CO}_2}$ vs $7.14 \text{ MJ/kg}_{\text{CO}_2}$). Furthermore, adopting intermediate solids storage (one or two vessels) showed to be effective in stabilizing the operation of calciner island (i.e., lower fluctuation of sorbent composition and limited variability of operating conditions of CaL reactors), while also reducing the calciner's size, the volume needed to store the CO_2 -rich gas and the amount of CO_2 sent to storage for a given amount of CO_2 captured from the EAF off-gas.
- For all the configuration simulated, the CaL plant was designed to capture over 90% of the CO_2 in the EAF off gas, resulting in a reduction of 94 $\text{kg}_{\text{CO}_2}/\text{t}_{\text{steel}}$ in EAF direct CO_2 emissions (Scope 1), corresponding to overall CO_2 capture rates of the CaL plant ranged between 91% and 93%. Using residual forestry biomass as calciner fuel enabled all configurations to achieved negative emissions. Potential CO_2 removal rates were in the order of 13 $\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2}/\text{h}$ for cases NST-V and 2ST, while they increased up to 27 $\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2}/\text{h}$ for cases NST-C and 1ST-C thanks to the higher fuel consumption. Furthermore, the estimated CO_2 removal rate relative to the steelmaking ranged from 100 to 200 $\text{kg}_{\text{CO}_2}/\text{t}_{\text{steel}}$. Lastly, it is worth noting that no additional electricity needs to be imported, as the CaL technology's possibility to recover high-temperature heat enables the self-generation of all the electricity required by the CO_2 capture plant via a heat recovery steam cycle, operating at constant load (as a result of the introduction of molten salts as thermal storage unit) with capacity ranging from 16 to 30 MW_{el} , depending on the configuration.
- The estimated CAPEX for the CaL plant configuration ranged from 193 M€ (2ST) to 270 M€ (NST-C). The adoption of intermediate solids storage contributes to reduce the initial investment, primarily due to the smaller calciner and CO_2 -reach gas holder volume. On the other hand, in the real system, implementing intermediate solid storages would add challenges related to operating large solids fluidised beds and increased complexity.

With a CCA (carbon tax) of 100 €/t_{CO_2} , which also is applied to estimate credits for negative emissions, the integration of the CaL technology to capture CO_2 in EAF steelmaking led to increments of steel cost between 26 $\text{€/t}_{\text{steel}}$ (2ST) and 36 $\text{€/t}_{\text{steel}}$ (NST-V), compared to the unabated EAF steelmaking process. These values correspond to 6%–9% of the global average levelized cost of scrap-EAF steel.

Case 2ST resulted in the lowest increment of steel cost thanks to its reduced CAPEX and fuel consumption.

Additionally, estimations were carried out to determine the CCA required for the CaL system to achieve cost parity with unabated EAF steelmaking—that is no increment of steel cost. The resulting CCA values were 255 €/t_{CO2} for NST-V, 208 €/t_{CO2} for NST-C, 202 €/t_{CO2} for 1ST-C, and 228 €/t_{CO2} for 2ST. Notably, the results for 1ST-C indicated that its higher fuel consumption—although less energy efficient due to higher specific fuel consumptions—led to greater revenues from negative CO₂ emissions, thereby enhancing the economic competitiveness of the CaL configuration with one intermediate solids storage and constant solid circulation. Moreover, a sensitivity analysis revealed that for carbon tax values exceeding 160 €/t_{CO2}, the 1ST-C case yielded lowest increment of steel cost. Conversely, for carbon tax values below 160 €/t_{CO2}, case 2ST had the lower increment of steel cost. Additional sensitivity analyses considering CAPEX variation ($\pm 50\%$), biomass price (50 - 120 €/t_{biomass}), and CO₂ transport and storage cost (10 - 50 €/t_{CO2}) consistently identified 2ST as the configuration with the lowest increment of steel cost across all examined scenarios.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Néstor D. Montiel-Bohórquez: Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation; **Manuele Gatti:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization; **Matteo C. Romano:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary material

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found in the online version at [10.1016/j.ccs.2025.100504](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccs.2025.100504).

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